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ABSTRACT

The paper studies the geometry of integrable Hamiltonian system. The basic concept of a Hamiltonian system of differential equations forms the basis of much of the more advanced work in classical mechanics, including motions of rigid bodies, celestial mechanics, quantization theory and so on. More recently, Hamiltonian methods have become increasingly important in the study of the equations of continuum mechanics, including fluids, plasmas and elastic media. It is shown that the level surfaces are three-dimensional surfaces with the positive or negative Gauss curvature at the point, where it is depend on which canonical form it has. All surfaces can be characterized by their Gaussian curvature, which describes the geometry of the surface: Euclidean, elliptic, or hyperbolic. Furthermore, curvature dictates how a vector may be transported across the surface or within the space.

Keywords: Poisson bracket, Hamiltonian function, completely integrable Hamiltonian system in the sense of Liouville, hyper space, 3-dimensional surfaces on 4-dimensional space, Gauss curvature.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

Let M be a smooth manifold of dimension m .

Definition 1 [3-5]. A *Poisson bracket* on a smooth manifold M is an operation that assigns a smooth real-valued function $\{F, H\}$ on M to each pair F, H of smooth, real-valued functions, with the basic properties:

(a) *Bilinearity*:

$$\begin{aligned} \{cF + c'P, H\} &= c\{F, H\} + c'\{P, H\}, \\ \{F, cH + c'P\} &= c\{F, H\} + c'\{F, P\}. \quad c, c' \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

(b) *Skew-Symmetry*:

$$\{F, H\} = -\{H, F\}$$

(c) *Jacobi Identity*:

$$\{\{F, H\}, P\} + \{\{P, F\}, H\} + \{\{H, P\}, F\} = 0$$

(d) *Leibniz' Rule*:

$$\{F, H \cdot P\} = \{F, H\} \cdot P + H \cdot \{F, P\}$$

A manifold M with a Poisson bracket is called *Poisson manifold*, the bracket defining *Poisson structure* on M .

Example 1.[3-4]. Let M be the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m , $m = 2n + l$ with coordinates

$(p, q, z) = (p^1, \dots, p^n, q^1, \dots, q^n, z^1, \dots, z^l)$. If $F(p, q, z)$ and $H(p, q, z)$ are smooth functions, we define their Poisson bracket to be the function:

$$\{F, H\} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^i} \cdot \frac{\partial F}{\partial q^i} - \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} \cdot \frac{\partial F}{\partial p^i} \right\}$$

We note the particular bracket identities:

$$\begin{aligned} \{p^i, p^j\} &= 0, \{q^i, q^j\} = 0, \{q^i, p^j\} = \delta_j^i, \\ \{p^i, z^k\} &= \{q^i, z^k\} = \{z^t, z^k\} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

in which i and j run from 1 to n , when t and k run from 1 to l . δ_j^i is the Kronecker symbol, which is 1 if $i = j$ and 0 otherwise.

Definition 2 [4-5]. Let M be a Poisson manifold and $H : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a smooth function. The *Hamiltonian vector field* associated with H is the unique smooth vector field $sgradH$ on M satisfying

$$sgradH(F) = \{F, H\} = -\{H, F\} \quad (1)$$

for every smooth function $F : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

The equations governing the flow of $sgradH$ are referred to as *Hamilton's equations* for the *Hamiltonian function* H .

In the case of the Poisson bracket on \mathbb{R}^m $m = 2n + l$, the Hamiltonian vector field corresponding to $H(p, q, z)$ is clearly

$$sgradH = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial p^i} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial q^i} - \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial p^i} \right)$$

The corresponding flow is obtained by integrating the system of ordinary differential equations

$$\frac{dq^i}{dt} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^i}, \frac{dp^i}{dt} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i}, i = 1, \dots, n, \frac{dz^j}{dt} = 0, j = 1, \dots, l$$

Which are *Hamiltonian systems* in this case. [1-3].

Proposition 1 [1,4,6]. Let M be a Poisson manifold and $F, H : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be smooth functions with corresponding Hamiltonian vector fields $sgradF, sgradH$. The Hamiltonian vector field associated with the Poisson bracket of F and H is, up to sign, the Lie bracket of the two Hamiltonian vector fields:

$$sgrad\{F, H\} = [sgradF, sgradH]$$

Let M^{2n} be a Poisson manifold and $sgradH$ Hamiltonian vector field with a smooth Hamiltonian function H.

Definition 3 [2,4]. Hamiltonian system $sgradH$ is called *completely integrable in the sense of Liouville*, if exists set of smooth functions f_1, \dots, f_n as:

- 1) f_1, \dots, f_n are first integrals of $sgradH$ Hamiltonian vector field,
- 2) they are functionally independent on M , that is, almost everywhere on M their gradients are linearly independent,
- 3) $\{f_i, f_j\} = 0$ for any i and j ,
- 4) the vector fields $sgradf_i$ are complete, that is natural parameter on their integral trajectories is defined on the whole number line [1].

Denote by Q the Riemannian ambient manifold. Let $dimQ = N$. For its metric is g^Q . Denote by M the n -dimensional manifold ($n < N$), the embedding $f : M \rightarrow Q$.

There are three vector bundles:

- 1) $TM = (P, X), P \in M, X \in T_pM$,
- 2) Normal bundle: $NM, (P, \xi), P \in M, \xi \in N_pM$,

$$m = dimN_pM = N - n$$

- 3) Q -bundle: $(P, \xi), P \in M, \xi \in N_pQ$.

$$T_pQ = T_pM \oplus N_pM$$

Definition 4 [2]. An n -dimensional surface M in an N -dimensional Euclidean space is called a hyper surface if $N = n + 1$.

If $Q = \mathbb{R}^N$ and $dimM = n, N = n + 1$, then T_pM is a hyper surface.

Definition 5 [2]. The normal section of the submanifold M at the point P , corresponding to existing pair $X \in T_pM$ and $\xi \in N_pM$ is the intersection of M with the 2-plane passing through X and ξ .

The normal section in a neighborhood of the point P is smooth regular curve on M .

Theorem 1 [2]. For any point $P \in M$ in the space T_pM there is a basis X_1, \dots, X_n in which the matrix of the first quadratic form is identity and matrix of the second quadratic form is diagonal:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \lambda_n \end{pmatrix} \tag{2}$$

Definition 6 [2]. The numbers λ_j are called the *principal curvatures* of the manifold M at the point P , and the lines passing through the vectors X_j are the *principal directions*.

The *Gaussian curvature* of the manifold M at the point P is:

$$K = \prod_{j=1}^n \lambda_j. \quad (3)$$

Let $Q = \square^4$ and $M \in \square^4$ and $\dim M = 3$.

Definition 7. At each point p of a 3-dimensional differentiable surface on 4-dimensional Euclidean space one may choose a unit normal vector. A normal plane at p is one that contains the normal vector, and will therefore also contain a unique direction tangent to the surface and cut the surface in a plane curve, called normal section. This curve will in general have different curvatures for different normal planes at p . The principal curvatures at p , denoted k_1 , k_2 and k_3 , are the extreme values of this curvature and that the corresponding directions called principal directions X_1, X_2, X_3 at p which are orthogonal.

Definition 8. The Gauss curvature of the 3-dimensional differentiable surface on 4-dimensional Euclidean space at a point is defined at the product of the principal curvatures where denoted by $K = k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3$.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let given 3-dimensional differentiable surface with the parametric equation as:

$$\begin{cases} p_1 = f^1(u, v, w) \\ p_2 = f^2(u, v, w) \\ q_1 = f^3(u, v, w) \\ q_2 = f^4(u, v, w) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

At each point of this surface has tangent plane with the basic vectors and a normal vectors as:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \{f_u^1, f_u^2, f_u^3, f_u^4\}, \\ r_2 &= \{f_v^1, f_v^2, f_v^3, f_v^4\}, \\ r_3 &= \{f_w^1, f_w^2, f_w^3, f_w^4\}, \\ \xi &= \{\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \xi_4\}. \end{aligned}$$

And vectors

$$\begin{aligned} r_{11} &= \{f_{uu}^1, f_{uu}^2, f_{uu}^3, f_{uu}^4\}, \\ r_{12} &= \{f_{uv}^1, f_{uv}^2, f_{uv}^3, f_{uv}^4\}, \\ r_{13} &= \{f_{uw}^1, f_{uw}^2, f_{uw}^3, f_{uw}^4\}, \\ r_{22} &= \{f_{vv}^1, f_{vv}^2, f_{vv}^3, f_{vv}^4\}, \\ r_{23} &= \{f_{vw}^1, f_{vw}^2, f_{vw}^3, f_{vw}^4\}, \\ r_{33} &= \{f_{ww}^1, f_{ww}^2, f_{ww}^3, f_{ww}^4\}. \end{aligned}$$

where f_j^i is partial derivative of f with respect to u, v, w , and f_{jk}^i is the mixed derivative of the second order and $i = \overline{1, 4}$.

These vectors are enough to write matrix of first quadratic form A and matrix of second quadratic form B .

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{pmatrix} \langle r_1, r_1 \rangle & \langle r_1, r_2 \rangle & \langle r_1, r_3 \rangle \\ \langle r_1, r_2 \rangle & \langle r_2, r_2 \rangle & \langle r_2, r_3 \rangle \\ \langle r_1, r_3 \rangle & \langle r_2, r_3 \rangle & \langle r_3, r_3 \rangle \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{12} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{13} & g_{23} & g_{33} \end{pmatrix} \\ B &= \begin{pmatrix} \langle r_{11}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{12}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{13}, \xi \rangle \\ \langle r_{12}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{22}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{23}, \xi \rangle \\ \langle r_{13}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{23}, \xi \rangle & \langle r_{33}, \xi \rangle \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{13} \\ b_{12} & b_{22} & b_{23} \\ b_{13} & b_{23} & b_{33} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

where bracket is inner product.

According to Theorem 1 we have following determinant:

$$\begin{vmatrix} b_{11} - kg_{11} & b_{12} - kg_{12} & b_{13} - kg_{13} \\ b_{12} - kg_{12} & b_{22} - kg_{22} & b_{23} - kg_{23} \\ b_{13} - kg_{13} & b_{23} - kg_{23} & b_{33} - kg_{33} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (5)$$

By calculating the determinant of the matrix we obtain for us a third-order equation required function k , where we can find formula for Gauss curvature of 3-dimensional surface on 4-dimensional space:

$$K = \frac{b_{11}(b_{22}b_{33} - b_{23}^2) + b_{12}(b_{13}b_{23} - b_{12}b_{33}) + b_{13}(b_{12}b_{23} - b_{13}b_{22})}{g_{11}(g_{23}^2 - g_{22}g_{33}) + g_{12}(g_{12}g_{33} - g_{13}g_{23}) + g_{13}(g_{13}g_{22} - g_{12}g_{23})} \tag{6}$$

Let us consider the Hamiltonian functions $H : M^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on the Poisson manifold M^4 which are given by the formulas

$$H(p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) = (-1)^i p_1^2 + (-1)^j p_2^2 + (-1)^k q_1^2 + (-1)^l q_2^2. \quad i, j, k, l = 1, 2.$$

There generates 3-dimensional surfaces on 4-dimensional space in each value of Hamiltonian function with the equations as

$$(-1)^i p_1^2 + (-1)^j p_2^2 + (-1)^k q_1^2 + (-1)^l q_2^2 = c. \quad i, j, k, l = 1, 2.$$

Theorem 2. Let surface can be written in canonical form as

$$(-1)^i p_1^2 + (-1)^j p_2^2 + (-1)^k q_1^2 + (-1)^l q_2^2 = 1.$$

If the value of all or one of i, j, k, l is equal to 2, then 3-dimensional surface has the positive Gauss curvature. In other cases, if the value of two or three of i, j, k, l is equal to 2, then 3-dimensional surface is the surface with the negative Gauss curvature.

Proof. First case: If all values of i, j, k, l are equal to 2, then

$$p_1^2 + p_2^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 = 1$$

the surface is the standart 3-dimensional sphere, so it is obvious that it's Gauss curvature is always positive.

Second case: If the one of values of i, j, k, l is equal to 2, then the equation of the surface can be as:

$$p_1^2 - p_2^2 - q_1^2 - q_2^2 = 1$$

Now we find A and B matrix for this surface.

Gauss curvature is not depend on choosing parameterization method, so we will parameterize it as:

$$\begin{cases} p_1 = chu \\ p_2 = shusinv \\ q_1 = shucosvcosw \\ q_2 = shucosvsinw \end{cases}$$

We have coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} g_{11} &= ch2u, & g_{12} &= 0, & g_{13} &= 0, \\ g_{22} &= sh^2u, & g_{23} &= 0, & g_{33} &= sh^2ucos^2v, \\ b_{11} &= -1, & b_{12} &= 0, & b_{13} &= 0, \\ b_{22} &= -sh^2u, & b_{23} &= 0, & b_{33} &= -sh^2ucos^2v. \end{aligned}$$

where vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \{shu, chusinv, chucosvcosw, chucosvsinw\}, \\ r_2 &= \{0, shucosv, -shusinvcosw, -shusinvsinw\}, \\ r_3 &= \{0, 0, -shucosvsinw, shucosvcosw\}, \\ \xi &= \{-chu, shusinv, shucosvcosw, shucosvsinw\}, \\ r_{11} &= \{chu, shusinv, shucosvcosw, shucosvsinw\}, \\ r_{12} &= \{0, chucosv, -chusinvcosw, -chusinvsinw\}, \\ r_{13} &= \{0, 0, -chucosvsinw, chucosvcosw\}, \\ r_{22} &= \{0, -shusinv, -shucosvcosw, -shucosvsinw\}, \\ r_{23} &= \{0, 0, shusinvsinw, -shusinvcosw\}, \\ r_{33} &= \{0, 0, -shucosvcosw, -shucosvsinw\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we ready to write the formula for the Gauss curvature

$$K = -\frac{b_{11}b_{22}b_{33}}{g_{11}g_{22}g_{33}} = \frac{shu^4 cos^2v}{ch2ushu^4 cos^2v} = \frac{1}{ch2u}$$

So, we proved that the surface has positive Gauss curvature.

If the surface is given with the equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_2^2 - p_1^2 - q_1^2 - q_2^2 &= 1 \quad \text{or} \\ q_1^2 - p_1^2 - p_2^2 - q_2^2 &= 1 \quad \text{or} \\ q_2^2 - p_1^2 - p_2^2 - q_1^2 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

We can choose a parameterization since the coefficients will be the same as the coefficients of the given surface.

Third case: If the two of values of i, j, k, l is equal to 2, then the equation of the surface can be as:

$$p_1^2 + p_2^2 - q_1^2 - q_2^2 = 1$$

Now we find A and B matrix for this surface.

Gauss curvature is not depend on choosing parameterization method, so we will parameterize it as:

$$\begin{cases} p_1 = chuchvcosw \\ p_2 = chuchvsinw \\ q_1 = chushv \\ q_2 = shu \end{cases}$$

where vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \{shuchvcosw, shuchvsinw, shushv, chu\}, \\ r_2 &= \{chushvcosw, chushvsinw, chuchv, 0\}, \\ r_3 &= \{chuchvsinw, chuchvsinw, 0, 0\}, \\ \xi &= \{-chuchvcosw, -chuchvsinw, chushv, shu\}, \\ r_{11} &= \{chuchvcosw, chuchvsinw, chushv, shu\}, \\ r_{12} &= \{shushvcosw, shushvsinw, shuchv, 0\}, \\ r_{13} &= \{-shuchvsinw, shuchvcosw, 0, 0\}, \\ r_{22} &= \{chuchvcosw, chuchvsinw, chushv, 0\}, \\ r_{23} &= \{-chushvsinw, chushvcosw, 0, 0\}, \\ r_{33} &= \{-chuchvcosw, -chuchvsinw, 0, 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

We have coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} g_{11} &= sh^2uch2v + ch^2u, & g_{12} &= 2chuchvshushv, & g_{13} &= 0, \\ g_{22} &= ch^2uch2v, & g_{23} &= 0, & g_{33} &= ch^2uch^2v, \\ b_{11} &= -1, & b_{12} &= 0, & b_{13} &= 0, \\ b_{22} &= -ch^2u, & b_{23} &= 0, & b_{33} &= -ch^2uch^2v. \end{aligned}$$

Now we ready to write the formula for the Gauss curvature

$$K = -\frac{b_{11}b_{22}b_{33}}{g_{33}(g_{12}^2 - g_{11}g_{22})} = \frac{1}{4ch^2vsh^2ush^2v - sh^2uch^22v - ch^2uch2v} = -\frac{1}{sh^2u + ch^2uch2v}$$

So, we proved that the surface has negative Gauss curvature.

If the surface is given with the equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_1^2 - p_2^2 - q_1^2 + q_2^2 &= 1 \quad \text{or} \quad p_1^2 - p_2^2 + q_1^2 - q_2^2 = 1 \quad \text{or} \\ p_2^2 - p_1^2 - q_1^2 + q_2^2 &= 1 \quad \text{or} \quad p_2^2 - p_1^2 + q_1^2 - q_2^2 = 1 \quad \text{or} \\ q_1^2 + q_2^2 - p_1^2 - p_2^2 &= 1 \quad \text{or} \quad q_1^2 - q_2^2 - p_1^2 + p_2^2 = 1 \quad \text{or} \\ q_2^2 - p_1^2 - p_2^2 - q_1^2 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

We can choose a parameterization since the coefficients will be the same as the coefficients of the given surface.

In the last case: If the three of values of i, j, k, l is equal to 2, then the equation of the surface can be as:

$$p_1^2 + p_2^2 - q_1^2 + q_2^2 = 1$$

Now we find A and B matrix for this surface.

Gauss curvature is not depend on choosing parameterization method, so we will parameterize it as:

$$\begin{cases} p_1 = chucosvcosw \\ p_2 = chucosvsinw \\ q_1 = shu \\ q_2 = chusinv \end{cases}$$

where vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \{shucosvcosw, shucosvsinw, chu, shusinv\}, \\ r_2 &= \{-chusinvcosw, -chusinvsinw, 0, chucosv\}, \\ r_3 &= \{-chucosvsinw, chucosvcosw, 0, 0\}, \\ \xi &= \{chucosvcosw, chucosvsinw, -shu, chusinv\}, \\ r_{11} &= \{chucosvcosw, chucosvsinw, shu, chusinv\}, \\ r_{12} &= \{-shusinvcosw, -shusinvsinw, 0, shucosv\}, \\ r_{13} &= \{-shucosvsinw, shucosvcosw, 0, 0\}, \\ r_{22} &= \{-chucosvcosw, -chucosvsinw, 0, -chusinv\}, \\ r_{23} &= \{chusinvsinw, -chusinvcosw, 0, 0\}, \\ r_{33} &= \{-chucosvcosw, -chucosvsinw, 0, 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

We have coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} g_{11} &= ch^2u, & g_{12} &= 0, & g_{13} &= 0, \\ g_{22} &= ch^2u, & g_{23} &= 0, & g_{33} &= ch^2ucos^2v, \\ b_{11} &= 1, & b_{12} &= 0, & b_{13} &= 0, \\ b_{22} &= -ch^2u, & b_{23} &= 0, & b_{33} &= -ch^2ucos^2v. \end{aligned}$$

Now we ready to write the formula for the Gauss curvature

$$K = -\frac{b_{11}b_{22}b_{33}}{g_{11}g_{22}g_{33}} = \frac{ch^4ucos^2v}{ch^4uch^2ucos^2v} = -\frac{1}{ch2u}$$

So, we proved that the surface has negative Gauss curvature.

If the surface is given with the equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_2^2 - p_1^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 &= 1 \quad or \\ p_1^2 - p_2^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 &= 1 \quad or \\ p_1^2 + p_2^2 + q_1^2 - q_2^2 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

We can choose a parameterization since the coefficients will be the same as the coefficients of the given surface.

So, proof is finished, we have proved theorem 2.

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